

Most Common Problems of ESL Learners in Writing: An Analysis

S. Basheer Ahmed¹, Prof. K. RatnaShiela Mani²

¹Research Scholar, Dept. of English, Acharya Nagarjuna University, Guntur - 522002, ybna.basheer@gmail.com

²Professor in the Department of English, Acharya Nagarjuna University, Guntur- 522002, ratnashielaamani@rediffmail.com

Abstract - Among the four basic communication skills of the English language, writing is looked like an incredibly challenging one to execute. Since writing is considered as a very formal mode of communication it demands perfection. A written composition should not only lucid in its message but also ideal in its construction. Any discrepancy in construction can lead to an ambiguity in the perception of the read message. Learners during their academic atmosphere look writing as a just tool through which they present their subjects in the exams. They do not consider writing a very important and inevitable weapon to lead the professional world. Learners often grumble on their own writing abilities, sometimes they complain against themselves and sometimes on their backgrounds, teachers, and academics. No matter what reason a person has for his bad writing ability but the problems in writing will undoubtedly cause a great damage to their success in production of ideas or information. This paper focuses on the most common problems in writing that the learners often show in their written composition and some effective strategies to be introduced to achieve perfection in writing of ESL learners.

Key Words: Writing Skills- Writing Problems- SWCs- Key strategies - Freewriting – Creative Writing – Motivation

I. INTRODUCTION

Writing is a decisive skill in language expression or in other words, an expressive construction of a language in a note. Writing is regarded as a very complicated task that requires extensive knowledge, understanding, and skill. It's a globally used mediation of information or knowledge. A proficient English language writer develops a text that is logical in construction, cohesive in an organization of sentences, lucid in structure, interesting in an expression of ideas through its fitting vocabulary and mechanism, Jacobs & L, (1981); Hall, (1988). Writing composition or expression through writing is becoming the most deserted skill among the primary skills of communication and there is no effective method for either teaching or evaluation of writing composition, Geisler, Hessler, Gardner, & Lovelace (2009). The assessment of written composition is basically through timed-essay in the examination and it has been applied in almost all the subjects, Caudery (1990) & Brown (2010). This type of assessment will only contribute to scoring and selection of the courses.

This study is an attempt to examine the writing problems of the undergraduate level engineering students of Rayalaseema region, Andhra Pradesh, India. The objective is to spot the problems and to recommend certain productive ways to help learners overcome the troubles and improve their writing abilities.

II. WRITING SKILLS

Skill in writing is a very significant facet that permits the writers to convey their ideas or thoughts and mental interactions through meaningful words that are sensibly integrated into messages, Knoch, May, Macqueen, Pill, & Storch (2016) & Jani, Mellinger, (2015). Writing skills help improve fluency, creativity in expressing thoughts or information in a better way so that the readers can comprehend with no trouble. Writing is an appropriate and

tactical use of language in written form with accuracy in structure and potentiality in communicating the content, Hyland, (2003). Kellogg (2001) opinioned that writing as a cognitive process that commonly examines the writer's memory, the ability of thinking, and command on words to productively convey his message or ideas (Nickerson, Perkins, & Smith, 2014).

III. WRITING PROBLEMS

Writing is not only an external act but also an internal cognitive process in which the writer has to make some efforts at the sentence and paragraph level through controlling the content, format, structure, vocabulary, spelling and punctuation in an artistic way, Flower, Hayes (1981). The learners of any level face diverse problems in writing at their different stages of learning. These problems are commonly classified into categories such as linguistic, cognitive, pedagogical and psychological predicaments of writing, Hyland, (2003). Students generally struggle with the structure related problems of English; structural trouble can make not only the content but also comprehension of the text be complicated and the reader may find trouble to interpret the thought in the content, Quintero, L. M. (2008). Among the problems that the learners have dealing with the second language, one is grammar, more particularly verbs that take different forms based on subject and tense that are used with, they make a problem in writing for ESL learners, Tyner (1987).

Students' cultural and regional backgrounds and learning styles also influence their writing abilities. It is also argued that the learners' poor writing skills are the consequences of two primary factors: the one is the teacher's approach and the other is learner's understanding. The pedagogic approach that a teacher follows to teach writing, facilitating with opportunities to learn, providing timely and constructive feedback, and most importantly motivating the learners towards writing practice are the key issues involved in the

teachers' approach. On the other hand, students' practice, motivation and the influence of mother tongue or L1 are the key issues involved in the learners' understanding towards the composition of a text, Bilal, H. A., Tariq, A. R., Din, N., Latif, H., & Anjum, M. N. (2013).

IV. RESEARCH PARADIGM

80 first-year engineering students of the Rayalaseema region were taken for the study as a sample. The objective of the study is to examine and analyze the key problems of the students through a written composition test. The most common problems that they constantly face while presenting their ideas during the composition of a written text were examined. The study was mainly focused to examine the problems that commonly roll out in writing such as, grammar, syntax, vocabulary, spellings, verb forms, and use of spoken expressions in writing. These problems are commonly seen in writing due to learners' varied backgrounds, lack of writing practices, cognitive inabilities, the influence of MT and L1, and lack of understanding of the ESL.

A. Procedure

The students were instructed to compose a 150 to 200 words essay on a given topic. The task was held inside the classroom and the students were given an hour's time to complete the composition. Each student's composition was evaluated, corrected, marked, and informed; the feedback was also given to the students. The topic given for composition was to describe their favorite personality or favorite tourist spot or favorite subject or anything that is their favorite.

B. The Evaluation

The 80 written compositions were examined, evaluated and marked by the researcher. The most common mistakes that were rolled out in the written compositions of the students were summarized in the following points. The errors shown below are to replicate the common sort of errors, there were other problems too observed.

- I *regularly visited* the holy town (Verb Forms error: Tense – 'visit' has to be used)
- It *is* my father who supported me in my childhood (Verb Forms: 'was' instead of 'is')
- Many times we *are visited* the place (Syntax: Active structure – 'visited / have visited')
- They *selled* us many such things (Verb forms: Sold)
- The *whether* was so nice and we stayed for two more days (Vocabulary: weather)
- We would have *gonn* mad if we *have invited* him to the function (spelling gone; Verb Forms: had invited)
- He loved it *bcoz* he once lost it in the bet (WhatsApp language: 'bcoz' instead of 'because')
- Their* were many *oppartunities* he had but he rejected and strongly decided to work only for his goal (inappropriate word: 'their' instead of 'there'; spelling: 'opportunities')
- Firstly* I would like to tell about his habits (Punctuation: a comma is omitted)

- You don't* know how he worked *very hardly* to win (Spoken Expression: informal 'you don't'; inappropriate word choice: 'hardly' instead of 'hard')
- Many great people born in *a* poor families *and* lived rich (Grammar: No article; inappropriate connector: 'but' has to be used)
- Ancient stories *written in the cave on the rocks* (Grammar: were written; Syntax: 'on the rocks of the cave' is the right use)

C. Data Analysis

There were many varied errors found among the compositions prepared by the students and most of them were common grammatical errors such as the tenses, agreement, prepositions and the other common problems were related to spelling, Syntax, Vocabulary or word choice, and redundancy associated errors. There were students who were slow in preparation of a written composition due to their regional and educational backgrounds and lack of practice observed; some students found difficulty in forming even simple sentences and using the right connectors; some other students had difficulty in developing or organizing their ideas in a coherent manner, it was due to cognitive disabilities relating to writing composition.

The evaluation of the written compositions was done in a detailed manner by highlighting the number of errors rolled out in certain categories and the scores were allocated by considering the errors one side and the success rate achieved in presenting the ideas or thoughts in adequate manner. Figure 1 and figure 2 show a replica of the evaluation of the students' written compositions (SWCs).

Fig.1. Example SWC 1

Fig. 2. Example SWC 2

Based on the errors rolled out and the scores achieved the students' written compositions (SWCs) were divided into four categories, the poor, the average, the moderate, and the efficient: the poor category SWCs carry very fewer scores i.e. $\leq 32\%$, 0 to 8 out of 25 marks; the average category SWCs carry scores between $36\% \geq \leq 52\%$ i.e. 9 to 13 out of 25 marks; the moderate category SWCs carry scores between $56\% \geq \leq 80\%$ i.e. 14 to 20 out of 25; the efficient category SWCs carry scores between $84\% \geq \leq 100\%$ i.e. 21 to 25 out of 25 marks. The SWCs which were evaluated and categorized are shown below in table 1.

TABLE 1. Category wise division of Written Compositions based on the Scores achieved by the students

Category wise division of Written Compositions based on the Scores achieved by the students				
Poor Between 0-8	Average Between 9-13	Moderate Between 14-20	Efficient Between 21-25	Total Number of SWCs
7	15	42	16	80

Table 1 shows the division of Students' Written Compositions (SWCs) category wise based on the scores achieved by the students. 7 out of 80 students achieved poor scores, between 0-8; 15 students scored average, between 9 - 13; 16 students achieved the efficient scores, between 21 -25; however, the highest number of students i.e. 42 scored moderate, between 14 -20. Table 2 and Graph 1 show the mean, mode, and SD values of the category wise SWCs.

TABLE 3. Frequent occurrence of most common problems in writing

Occurrence of Most Common Problems (Errors) identified in the Students' Written Compositions (SWCs)							
Language Aspects	Poor (Total SWCs: 7)	Average (Total SWCs: 15)	Moderate (Total SWCs: 42)	Efficient (Total SWCs: 16)	Frequency of Occurrence (Among all the SWCs: 80)	Mean	S.D
Grammar	7	11	26	2	46	11.5	10.34408
Syntax	7	8	14	3	32	8	4.546061
Vocabulary	6	11	22	3	42	10.5	8.346656
Spelling	4	6	11	2	23	5.75	3.86221
Verb forms	5	7	12	3	27	6.75	3.86221
Spoken Expressions	2	2	3	1	8	2	0.816497
Other Errors	6	6	12	5	29	7.25	3.201562

TABLE 2. Category wise: number of SWCs, Mean, Mode, and SD Values

Category wise number of SWCs, Mean, Mode, & SD Values				
	Poor 0-8	Average 9-13	Moderate 14-20	Efficient 21-25
No. of SWCs	7	15	42	16
Mean	6.5714286	11.06666667	18.0952381	22
Mode	8	13	20	22
S.D	0.9759001	1.533747356	1.884591226	0.816496581

The total SWCs in poor category are 7 that has the mean score 6.571428571, the mode score 8, and the standard deviation 0.975900073; the total SWCs in average category are 15 that has the mean score 11.06666667, the mode 13, and the standard deviation 1.533747356; the total SWCs in moderate category are 42, the mean score 18.0952381, the mode 20, and the standard deviation 1.884591226; whereas the total SWCs in the efficient category are 16, the mean score 22, the mode 22, and the standard deviation 0.816496581. The highest number of students are seen in the moderate category and the second highest in the efficient category, if both the categories of SWCs are clubbed together then the total will reach to 70% above and even the mean, mode and SD values of the two groups show a very significant score as well. Hence, it is evidential that the chosen samples are not exceptionally poor in English but carry a considerable knowledge in the use of language to its acceptable level.

Graph 1. Category wise: number of SWCs, Mean, Mode, and SD Values

Table 3 and Graph 2 illustrate mean, mode, and SD values along with the number of frequent occurrence of the errors which were identified in the students' written compositions in relation to varied language aspects.

Graph 2. Mean and SD values of the frequent occurrence of the most common problems identified in the SWCs

Table 3 and graph 2 clearly affirm the values of mean and standard deviation which were calculated from the identification and evaluation of the total SWCs. The mean values of grammar, vocabulary, syntax, other errors, verb forms, spellings, and spoken expressions are notified to 11.5, 10.5, 8, 7.25, 6.75, 5.75, and 2 respectively; whereas the standard deviation of grammar, Vocabulary, Syntax, Spelling & Verb forms, other errors, and spoken expressions is 10.3440804, 8.34665602, 4.54606057, 3.86221008 & 3.86221008, 3.20156212, and 0.81649658 respectively. The mean value, 11.5 and standard deviation, 10.3440804 of grammar and the mean value of Vocabulary, 10.5, syntax, 8 are the higher scores noted than all the other language aspects; whereas the standard deviation of grammar, 10.3440804, Vocabulary, 8.34665602, and Syntax, 4.54606057 make the higher scores than the other language aspects. Thus, it makes very clear that the high frequency of the occurrence of errors in writing is associated to grammar, vocabulary, and syntax while the other language aspects such as spellings, verb forms, and spoken expressions have less significance in occurrence, comparing to the former set of problems.

Another set of problems identified in the SWCs other than the above most common and frequent problems were related to cohesion, repetition of sentences or ideas, use of inappropriate connectors, though these problems did not occur frequently in written compositions but they are needed to be observed. In a few SWCs the influence of WhatsApp language was also identified.

V. EFFECTIVE STRATEGIES TO IMPROVE WRITING

Applying some notable strategies during teaching-learning writing can improve learners' writing skills to the agreeable level by reducing the erroneous formation of the text. Initiation of technology, motivation, participating in interesting activities, peer to peer discussions, and feedback are a few effective strategies to develop learners' writing skills.

Initiation of technology: In recent years, research has been progressively stirred by social perceptions on learning online

platforms, very particularly, online learning through constructivist and social learning theories, Hrastinski, (2009). Technology can help learners understand, improve and perfect their written composition abilities. The initiation and understanding of computer, internet and some significant applications or websites that help improve writing skills will bring lucrative results. Preparing a text on a computer provides ease in forming grammatical sentences and makes the text almost error free, for instance, the websites on internet such as Grammarly, Small SEO tools, Grammar checker, Searchenginereports.com, Prepostseo.com, etc., help prepare text with grammatically correct sentences.

Motivation: Most teachers fail to improve teaching-learning writing skills among their learners through innovative strategies, as it was identified by, Nik, Sani, (2010) undergraduate level ESL learners are not provided certain motivation towards improving writing skills. To learn things, one needs motivation either external or internal. External motivation is a stimulus that the learners get from outside environment such as from teachers, from their peers, from the requirements and needs, and the other external sources. The internal motivation is a stimulus that learners have themselves within but not from the outside world, for instance, writing experiences and events everyday in a diary, preparing notes on a particular topic, following running notes during a lecture without the teacher's force etc., The teacher who has to act as a facilitator must motivate learners towards writing, correct them whenever it is necessary and give feedback, according to Skinner, language learning is a deliberate, strenuous process of consecutive estimations. It's programmed, structured classroom practices, while strengthening right responses and promptly correcting the wrong ones in a constructive manner, Valdman (1966).

Interesting activities: Due to thoughtless writing sessions, most of the learners look writing as an activity which is rarely happens, and they try to escape from any writing task after developing a pessimistic stance towards writing, and as a result, they recognize writing as a very difficult skill to be acquired, Demir (2011). The process of successful teaching-learning of writing is chiefly depends on the assessment of writing, Jones (2002). The involvement and practice play a crucial role in learning writing, to involve learners in writing, the teacher must act as a very important facilitator who can make learners participate and practice in various interesting activities which are related to writing. For instance, introducing free-writing, creative writing activities, asking for preparing projects, reports, giving a task to search and prepare a written notes on a historical context, and instigating research etc., Creative writing activities facilitate learners expose their creativity of using what they know to reveal what they can craft in the text, it also provides learners ample opportunities to discover and realize the importance of writing, Essex (1996), Tompkins (1982).

The constant initiation of varied practices of involving the learners into writing practices will surely develop students' efficiency in writing skills.

VI. CONCLUSION

By taking the findings, from the study into consideration, it is concluded that the most common problems of ESL students are primarily related to Grammar, Vocabulary, and Syntax and the problems related to Spellings, Verb forms, and Spoken expressions take the second position of importance to consider for examination and also required perfection. It is also observed that some of the learners find problems in the execution of data in written form though they come from English medium learning backgrounds; it is because of lack of practice in expressing their English Language skills in common contexts other than academics. However, the practice, motivation through creative ways, and regular participation and presentation of English language make a learner's written abilities perfect.

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